

ECHOES OF GENDER INEQUALITY IN THE PANDEMIC ERA

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Abstract

Recent studies indicate a sharp rise in sexual violence in Nigeria since the Covid-19 pandemic era. Rape and paedophilia are often perceived as socially constructed gender perversion against women and girls that are stereotypically vulnerable. However, the pandemic has exacerbated the rape of men and boys by perpetrators who are males or females. This study explores how sex myths, stigmatization among other rape supporting cultures inhibit the report of rape cases by male and female victims, examines the extent cases of rape of men and boys echoes gender perversion and questions the notion that rape and pedophilia are social construct nourished by patriarchal structures. As its theoretical framework, this article relies on Gender theory and the Freudian Psychoanalytic theory which asserts that a people's mutually developed beliefs about sexual difference, their interpretations of its significance and their reliance on those beliefs and interpretations justify the unequal treatment of women and men. The study engages qualitative research design while analysing the news media, newspaper reports and the social media, as its primary sources of data. The cases reviewed reveal that rape is not a social construct against women but a gender neutral crime hence men and women, boys and girls are victims of sexual perversion. The study is a significant contribution to gender studies. It provides a critical lens for examining the ideology of sexual behaviours in the pandemic era and offers a robust basis for categorising sexual revolution.

Keywords: gender inequality, perversion, rape, pedophilia, Covid 19 pandemic, social construct.

Introduction

Women constitute a marginalised population whose vulnerability increased in the face of the Covid-19 pandemic. The Corona Virus outbreak and the attendant preventive measures such as total or partial economic shutdown and

restrictions in movement did not only expose millions of women world over to gender-based violence, but heightened the upsurge of recorded rape cases in Nigeria and as such widening the gender inequality gaps and perpetuating forms of subordination. Prior to the pandemic in Nigeria, the UN report shows that 1 out of 4 girls experienced sexual violence. This number represents 30 per cent of girls and women aged between 15 and 49 (*Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018*). Though insurgency and the protracted conflict in the North East of Nigeria as well as entrenched gender discriminatory norms and a pervasive culture of impunity in the southern province of the country have served to exacerbate the occurrence of sexual violence against women in the country, however, the news media reports underscore the notion that the COVID-19 outbreak brought in not just a terrifying but a perverse phase of rape incidents in the country. In May 2020, the Nigerian Police reported 717 rape incidents across the country as a result of the COVID-19 restrictions (The Guardian, 16 June, 2020). Also, data from the National Early Warning System (NEWS) indicated that sexual violence cases in Nigeria increased by over 100% from 308 in January to over 3000 reported cases by May 31, 2020. This figure though alarming constitute a figment of the number of unreported cases of sexual violence across the country. Akintayo et al. (2019) in a call for concern identified rape as being endemic. Perversion in the context of this article is an act of thinking which include forceful sexual activity or fantasy directed towards orgasm other than genital intercourse with a willing partner of the opposite sex and of similar maturity, persistently recurrent, not merely a substitute for preferred behaviour made difficult by the immediate environment and contrary to the generally accepted norm of sexual behaviour in the community.

Gender prevention programmes often lay premium on rape of female victims but pay less attention to male victims. The law on rape continues to be gender sensitive as the default in discussions and studies about perverse gender acts is to think boys or men are perpetrators and women and girls as victims. Recent studies have examined different trends and patterns of violence against women and girls such as abduction, denial of resources, domestic violence, early and forced marriage, intimate partner violence, and sexual violence. Sadly, studies tend to ignore the fact that male rape has become a social issue given the rise in number of cases. It is a form of sexual violence that deserves recognition because of the similar devastating effects it shares with female rape. What is at stake here is not whether these patterns of violence exist or the

extent of pervasion, but just as it occurs in girls and women. Violation of men and boys also involve physical force or emotional coercion. Perpetrators in those cases other than boys and men can be girls and women. It becomes apparent that the problem of gender perversion against women cannot be addressed without solving the rape of men and boys. Since men are also harmed by gender roles and most males who have been raped hardly tell their stories as it is often the case among female victims; attention should be paid to male rape with the aim to advocate for gender equality advocacy. Male rape victims may not be accused as girls often are of interpreting a consensual sexual encounter as nonconsensual but may be accused of taking such assaults too seriously. The fundamental point of departure in this article consists in the claim that, violence against women and girls echoes a socially entrenched gender inequality and they form part of an organized, regulated and motivated system of power that is nourished by patriarchal structures. Therefore, if violence against women is understood as structural or systemic, an expression of discrimination and not just as direct violence, what becomes of the rape of male adults and children? Is male rape an exercise of power and control over the victim? If so, does generalising sexual violence echo gender inequality? How does constructs of gender and sexuality affect understanding of male rape and their views of men as victims of rape? The objectives of this article include: to interrogate rape and pedophilia as socially constructed forms of gender inequality that has been highlighted by the Covid-19 pandemic; to verify to what extent cases of rape of male adults and children echoes gender perversion; to unveil the socially constructed rape myths and supportive cultures that have served to exacerbate rape occurrences against adult males and boys since the pandemic era.

Methodology

To critically analyze this problem, the article reviewed both selected Newspapers such as Punch, Vanguard, The Guardian newspapers and Television Channels like TVC and Channels Televisions as well as the Sahara Reporters' online pages to extract cases and opinions that align with the Gender and Freudian theories that guided this study. Though rape cases are underreported (UN Women 2020), the news media report gave the few reported cases used for this study a wide publicity while analysis was based on the interpretation evident in the cases. The news media outlets chosen are all national dailies, thus their reports enjoy widespread coverage. Five cases of rape were selected for their uniqueness and the concern they generated both

online and offline. They occurred between the period of nationwide lockdown and the resumption of human and economic activities in 2020 until present. The rape cases unveiled the victims as objects of aggressive sexual gratification by sexual predators. The theoretical subsection presents the understanding of rape against women as a form of gender perversion, and discusses how these perverse acts expressed as social construction of inequality has exacerbated during COVID-19 pandemic. Then, the cases that form our statistical research engage the qualitative discourse analysis in arriving at its conclusion. Questionnaires were also administered to further investigate the occurrence of the rape of adult males and boys.

Discussions and Findings

Rape as a Social Construct: The UN in its April 2020 *Policy Brief: the impact of Covid-19 on Women* observed that the pandemic is deepening pre-existing gender inequalities while gender-based violence is increasing exponentially on a global scale. This fact undoubtedly reveals the fragility and vulnerability of women gender. In Nigeria also, the situation is even helpless as sex myths and rape support culture make it difficult to report cases of sexual violence and the support systems are not functional. There have been cases of fathers raping daughters and sometimes inviting their friends to do the same (UN 2020). This therefore emphasizes that rape as perversion is related to normal and aberrant modes of human sexuality. For the purpose of this article, rape could be term as sexual intercourse (oral, anal or vaginal penetration) without the consent of the victim.

Rape Cases in the Pandemic Era

Raped on transit: TVC Crime Watch on 4th June, 2020 featured a pathetic rape case which happened along Abuja – Akure road. The victim identified as Lady Courage is a 21years old lady who is in a business of transporting agricultural products from Akure to Abuja. On 4th June, 2020 she boarded a taxi from Jabi in Abuja to Ibadan. When she sensed that she was the only female passenger, she decided to throw up rude disposition towards the male passengers and the driver. While the journey was on course, one of the passengers seated close to her started making sexual advances. She raised alarm to scare him but other passengers responded that she was being rude while the driver shunned her. She then decided to make a video as an evidence to make a report at the next available police checkpoint. When they approached a military security post,

she alighted and complained to a soldier showing him the video she made as an evidence of the molestation and danger of a possible rape. She equally insisted that she was not willing to continue her journey for fear of being raped. Sadly, the soldier who conversed in Hausa language with the accused male passenger threatened that if she refuses to continue her journey with the other passengers; she will be quarantined as a Covid -19 patient for embarking on an illegal journey during a lockdown. Out of fear, she joined the car again and was eventually raped.

The sad story of Lady Courage is among the 3600 cases of women announced by the Minister of Women Affairs Senator Paullen Tallen on 16th July, 2020 who were reported raped during the lockdown. Her case shows that rape as gender perversion is a social construct motivated by power, anger and sexuality. The military personnel who should serve as a support system to prevent the rape instead exerted his power as a man and then as a soldier. He also displays his disgust of the female gender that circumstance has brought in the midst of male commuters. One wonders why the other male passengers were not threatened of being quarantined for making an illegal journey as well. The obvious response is seen in Susan Brownmiller's assertion that rape is not about a natural or biological need, but rather it is grounded in political motivations to dominate. The video she made was part of her flight response which eventually could not earn her protection instead she was threatened and she succumbed to tonic immobility- fear of being harmed that incapacitates a rape victim and prevents her from fighting back. Shifting the burden to women could have the problematic effect of reifying stereotypical notions about women's complicity in rape. Historically, women have been told to avoid rape by restricting their choices, movements, and behavior. A great deal of attention is placed, both inside the courtroom and in public perception, on whether the victim was dressed in a sexually provocative manner or whether proof of consent or lack of credibility can be gleaned from past sexual experiences. Lady Courage thus pledges anonymity to evade suchlike rape supportive myths which only serve to launch her into self-blame. Her case further confirms that women's bodies are marked only by a structural vulnerability that is undeniable and inescapable (Brownmiller 2019). The male passengers and the soldier who mediated when she complained all collaborated to perfect the crime confirming Chasseguet-Smirgel (1985) who said that "Perversions are a dimension of the human psyches in general, a temptation in the mind common to us all"(1). This implies that the whole being is involved and perverse acts are premeditated. Their collaboration suggests that female sexuality can be purchased or stolen.

Date Rape On April 27, 2020, the Punch Newspaper reported a case of gang rape in Kaduna State. The Victim Jennifer is reported by her sister to have been invited by one of the victim's male friends to an isolated location. On arrival to the place, she met two other girls and six boys. One of the boys had previously asked her for an intimate relationship. When it was time for the other two girls to leave, the victim also stood up to go, but one of the boys asked her to stay back for a private discussion with her on behalf of the boy who had asked her out. She stayed back because she trusted them. They offered her alcohol, which she declined, they coerced her into taking it after which she lost consciousness. Five boys took turns to rape her, while the sixth kept threatening the others to stop or he would report them, but he never did. After they had raped her, the boys dropped her around 7 pm by the bridge close to her house and called her friends to come and get her, alleging that she had been sleeping since morning. It was reported that she was taken to hospital because she was unconscious. Her case was reported to Barnawa Police Station the same night. Jennifer's case is similar to Lady Courage in that the act is a premeditated gender perversion motivated by concealed anger. The rape support myth that a woman's body is a battlefield and as such deserves the violence it got explains the purpose of this perversion- to steal the female sexuality they desire because they lack the necessary social and economic means of acquiring it legitimately. It is a concrete example of gender violence that reinforces male dominance and gender oppression. The perpetrators coerced her to become intoxicated which dulled her consciousness. In this state, she is unable to fight back or raise alarm.

Raped in a Church Vanguard Newspaper reported the sad rape story of a 22 year old student of the University of Benin who was raped and murdered in a church. On the 27th May 2020, late Uwaila Vera Omozuwa had gone to a church to read following the lockdown of higher institutions due to COVID-19 when she was raped, brutally beaten and killed. Uwa had complained about the disturbance of family members while studying at home, hence her choice of the church premises. The rapists narrated that they were paid one million naira by a suspected woman ritual to collect the blood of the girl for an alleged ritual. When they entered the church, they initiated a conversation with their target, attacked and raped her. They cleaned her blood and escaped before they were later arrested. She later died in the hospital and a post mortem examination confirmed that she was raped. (Vanguard newspaper June 12, 2020) What it was in her behavior, her manner, her dress that triggered this awful act against her? The answer lies in the male ideology of rape- a display of male domination. This agrees with Nagel who opines that “perversion is found in

how the constellation of sexuality, desire and the flesh are thought, not the way this constellation fits into established sexual definitions and meanings (5). Thus, as far as gender perversion is the motive no location is a safe haven. Male perpetrators seem to be taking advantage of lesser security, increased impunity, more limited reporting mechanisms, and reduced access to an already weak justice system during the pandemic to commit sexual violence (UN Women, 2020).

Boarding school rape case Vanguard Newspaper (Dec, 20, 2021) report of Don-Davies Archibong, an 11 years Junior Secondary School student of Deeper Life High School in Uyo, Akwai Ibom State who was allegedly molested and assaulted by senior boys, leaving him emotionally unstable, sick trended on many social media platforms, proving that rape is not exclusive to females. The mother of the male victim, Deborah Okezie had posted a video on her Facebook page where she recounted how her son Don Davies was sexually abused between October and December 2020 by senior students in his school. Don Davies was moved from his original hostel to a senior hostel of the school as punishment for bed-wetting despite the fact that the mother had pleaded that he be allowed to use macintouch on his bed but the hostel master resisted. Upon moving in among the senior boys, they started maltreating him sexually, they will remove his pants, pushing their hands and legs into his anus which eventually left him with a turn anus. He was starved and threatened not to tell anyone. Mrs Okezie raised alarm when she arrived upon school closure to pick up her son and saw how sickly he appeared. When the school could not give a satisfying answer, she took to the public space to demand for justice. She equally dragged the school to court after several medical investigations confirmed that Don Davies was serially raped. This case attracted varied public reactions. It further shows perpetrators of rape against boys are males as well. This case also represent many unreported boarding school, sports team rape that firmly confirm the vulnerability of males in enclosed space as attested to by many responses to the questionnaire. After lingered court trials of the perpetrators, the case was settled out of court possibly because of the reputation of the institution involved and the trauma of the victim being viewed as a homosexual. This trauma constitutes a sex myth that has inhibited male rape reports.

In May, 2022, Sahara Reporters published a story of Monsiri from Adamawa State, North East Nigeria born of dwarfism who was raped but a man identified as Didi. He was cheerful 1 young man who was mistaken for a

teenager. He was lured by Didi to his home and when alone with Monsiri, he raped him. Monsiri quickly reported to his mother who further went the perpetrators house to report the incidence. Rahab, Monsiri's mother could not report to the police when Didi's father visited the victim's mother and pleaded with her to let the issue slide. Monsiri's mother accepted to withdraw the matter from public attention because they were related and the father if Didi was a respected title-holder in the community. Didi is a serial rapist who has been convicted once for raping a minor. It was alleged that immediately the news of his rape broke out, Didi fled for fear of being arrested and sent to jail again. Monsiri's case is one out of many male victims who make the incidence known. Most men consider it shameful to report rape case because they believe that it is childish for a man to cry. Sadly, reported cases such as Monsiri's is treated with levity or out rightly dismissed resulting in subsuming of subsequent similar cases.

Conclusion

The concern of this article has been to investigate rape and pedophilia as gender perversion. Cases reviewed show that rape is socially constructed as a crime against both women and men motivated by power, anger and sexuality. Though rape has been a major violence against women in history, the Covid -19 pandemic has exacerbated its pervasive occurrence showing that rape and pedophilia should be construed not as social construct against women but as a gender neutral crime hence men and women , boys and girls are victims. While these cases reviewed represent vast majority of unreported cases, it reveals that rape supporting beliefs exist both for women as well as men. These have held back victims from reporting many cases of rape. Since rape is a neuter- gender construct, efforts should concentrate on how to eradicate rape support cultures.

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